

OCTOBER TO DECEMBER 1971:

RESEARCH SCHEDULE

Study of pre-Islamic pottery and other material in Iran 1966 to 1971

It is hoped to complete the research project within the next two years according to the following schedule:

JANUARY TO APRIL 1972:

SEPTEMBER 1971: Survey and investigation of pearling sites in Bahrain and
Examination of excavated material at Tepe Yahya in Iran and at the National
Museum in Kuwait. Abu Dhabi will be visited to advance negotiations on
field work for the spring of 1972.

Completion of Oxford and London of a final report on pearling and commerce

(1971)

OCTOBER TO DECEMBER 1971:

Completion in Oxford of my doctoral thesis draft entitled: "Archaeological
and documentary material for the history and mechanisms of commerce in
Southern Iran from the seventh century to the end of the Portuguese Period."
Collection of initial documentary material concerning the southern side of
the Persian Gulf and preparation for fieldwork.

JANUARY TO MAY 1972:

Archaeological survey and investigation of pearling sites on the coast of
Abu Dhabi and of the Northern Trucial States, including a study of pottery
and other artefacts collected on the survey.

JUNE TO SEPTEMBER 1972:

Completion of records and maps from the archaeological survey together with
documentary research on archaeological references to pearls and pearling.

OCTOBER TO DECEMBER 1972:

Study of pre-Islamic pottery and shells from my survey in Iraq 1968 to 1971 stored in the excavation house at Siraf.

JANUARY TO APRIL 1973:

Archaeological survey and investigation of pearling sites in Bahrain and Qatar, and if necessary, completion of work in the Trucial States.

MAY TO SEPTEMBER 1973:

Composition at Oxford and London of a final report on pearling and commerce in the Persian Gulf, 400 B.C. to 1000 A.D..

It will be seen that I hope to spend two terms at Oxford, one at the beginning and a second at the end of the two year period.